

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF RASAPRAKASH SUDHAKAR**¹Dr. Ankush Vishwanath Madavi, ²Dr. Mamta Tulshiram Kolte**

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, Sai Ayurved Medical College and Research Institute, Khandala, Vaijapur, Dist. Chh. Sambhajinagar.

²Final Year PG Scholar, Department of Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana, KAHER's Shri BMK Ayurveda Mahavidyalaya, Belagavi, Karnataka.

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Corresponding Author*Dr. Ankush Vishwanath Madavi**

Assistant Professor, Department of
Rasashastra and Bhaishajya
Kalpana, Sai Ayurved Medical
College and Research Institute,
Khandala, Vaijapur, Dist. Chh.
Sambhajinagar.

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ABSTRACT

Rasashastra, is a branch of Ayurveda, primarily focuses on the processing, purification, and therapeutic application of metals, minerals, *Ratna* (gemstones), and mercury-based formulations. Among the classical texts of *Rasashastra*, *Rasaprakash Sudhakar* is one of the most important texts due to its systematic presentation of pharmaceutical principles and medicinal preparations. Authored by Acharya Yashodhara Bhatta, this text is important source for understanding both the theoretical and practical aspects of pharmaceutics. This text includes a wide range of topics, including *Parada Samskara*, *Parada Bandha*, *Dhatu Shodhana* and *Marana*, *Maharasa*, *Uparasa*, *Ratna*, pharmaceutical (*Yantras*) instruments, and various therapeutic formulations. The present review provides a chapter-wise analysis of *Rasaprakash Sudhakar* and highlights its unique contributions to the development of Rasashastra literature.

KEYWORDS: *Rasashastra*, *Rasaprakash Sudhakar*, *Parada*, *Samskara*, *Ayurvedic Pharmaceutics*, *Rasaushadhi*.

INTRODUCTION

Rasashastra is a specialized branch of *Ayurveda* deals with the pharmaceutical processing and therapeutic utilization of metals, minerals, mercury, *Ratna* (gemstones), and herbo-

mineral preparations. Over centuries, lots of classical texts have contributed to the development of this field by documenting methods of *Shodhana* (purification), *Marana* (incineration), medicinal preparation, and clinical applications.

Among these texts, *Rasaprakash Sudhakar* describe systematic presentation of *Rasashastra* principles. The work was authored by *Acharya Yashodhara Bhatta*, who collect and compiled critically presented knowledge from earlier authorities while experiencing them.

The present review aims to provide a chapter-wise overview of *Rasaprakash Sudhakar* and to explore its significance in the historical and pharmaceutical development of *Rasashastra*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The present data have been taken from *Rasaprakash Sudhakar* along with its available commentaries and supporting classical Ayurvedic literature. This text consists of 13 *Adhyayas* (Chapters) and the contents of the text were discussed chapter-wise to understand its structure and contribution to the field of *Rasashastra*.

Chapter 1

The first chapter begins with *Vandana* (prayer) to Lord Shiva, Goddess Saraswati, Lord Ganesha, and *Parada* (mercury). The chapter provides a detailed knowledge of the origin, importance, and therapeutic significance of mercury.

In this chapter major focus on the description of eighteen *Samskaras* of *Parada*, which are very important to enhance the efficacy, stability, and safety of mercury. The chapter also discusses *Doshas* (defects) associated with improperly processed mercury.

Chapter 2

The second chapter explains the concept of *Bandha*, the process by which mercury is stabilized and suitable for medicinal use. Four types of *Parada Bandha* are described, namely *Jalauka Bandha*, *Khota Bandha*, *Pata Bandha*, and *Bhasma Bandha*.

The chapter further classifies substances uses in the binding process to increase their relative effectiveness. Herbal substances author mentions (Mullika) are considered best for achieving stable mercury preparations. With *Ratna* (gemstones) is medium, with *Suvarna* (*Dhatus*) as low and with *Putiloha* (*Naga*, *Vanga*) is considered as least.

Chapter 3

In this chapter various forms of mercury ash (*Parada Bhasma*) and their classification based on color, preparation techniques, and therapeutic utility described. Such as *Shweta* (White), *Krishna* (Black), *Peeta* (Yellowish), and *Rakta Bhasma* (Red) are described along with formulations including *Rasaparpati*, *Rasakarpura*, and *Rasasindura*.

In addition, the chapter explains the extraction of mercury from *Hingula* (cinnabar).

Chapter 4

The fourth chapter discusses *Dhatus* (metallic substances) used in Ayurvedic pharmaceutic with their purification (*Shodhana*) and incineration (*Marana*). Detailed descriptions are provided for gold, silver, copper, iron as *Shuddha Loha*, lead, tin as *Putiloha* and brass, white copper, and bronze as *Mishra Loha*.

Author mentioned 9 *dhatu*s but wrongly says 8 *dhatu*s in *shloka*.

Chapter 5

This chapter deals with *Maharasa* substances, The text describes their properties, classifications, and pharmaceutical applications.

Substances such as *Abhraka* (*Gagana*), *Rasaka*, *Vaikranta*, *Vimala*, *Sasyaka*, *Rajavarta*, and *shailasambhuta* (*shilajit*) are discussed. The chapter serves as a important resource for understanding the mineral materials utilized in *Rasashastra*.

Chapter 6

The sixth chapter provides a detailed knowledge of *Uparasa* substances, including *Talaka*, *Gandhaka*, *Kankushta*, *Gairika*, *Kasisa*, *kunati*, *Anjana*. Their physical characteristics, pharmaceutical processing, and medicinal uses are discussed.

The chapter ends with descriptions of *Sadharana Rasa* substances with their features.

Chapter 7

Ratnas (Gemstones) has a significant place in *Rasashastra*, and this chapter explores the concept of *Navaratna* and their relation with the nine *Navagraha*. Various types of *ratnas* are described along with methods of identification, purification (*Shodhana*), and incineration (*Marana*).

Chapter 8

In this chapter author compiles approximately one hundred *Rasa Yogas* intended for the management of various disease conditions. All these *yogas* are collected from different *Rasashastra* texts after understanding and experiencing them.

Chapter 9

This chapter describes sixty-four *Divyaushadhis* that are useful in various mercury-processing procedures such as *Bandha*, *Jarana*, *Marana*, and *Niyamana*. It also includes descriptions of sixty-eight *Rasaushadhis*, sixty-eight *Mahaushadhis*, and sixty-eight *Siddhaushadhis*.

Many of the drugs mentioned in this chapter are controversial and not even mentioned in *Nighantu* texts.

Chapter 10

Important chapter of the text, this chapter represents a detailed knowledge of pharmaceutical equipment's and instruments used in *Rasashastra*.

mentions forty *Yantras* used in various pharmaceutical procedures, fifteen types of *Musha* (crucibles), four types of *Koshti* (furnaces), and numerous varieties of *Putra* with their size.

Chapter 11

This chapter discusses 20 procedures related to *Hemakarana* and 17 procedures of *Ropyakarana*. the chapter also mentions methods for preparing artificial pearl (*Moti*) and coral (*Praval*).

Chapter 12

This chapter focuses on *Vajikarana* formulations aims to improves reproductive health, and physical strength including *Gutika* and *Leha* formulations, are described.

Chapter 13

The final chapter discusses formulations related to reproductive health. Various dosage forms, including *veeryasthambhaka Vati*, *Churna*, and *lepa*, are described.

The chapter concludes with the purpose of the text and information about the author's family.

CONCLUSION

Rasaprakash Sudhakar is one of the most important classical texts of *Rasashastra*. Through its thirteen chapters, the text comprehensively addresses mercury processing, metallic and mineral drugs, *Ratna* (gemstone) preparations, pharmaceutical instruments (*Yantras*), and

therapeutic formulations. The systematic presentation with practical pharmaceutical applications, makes the text an important contribution to Ayurvedic literature.

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